

26-03-2024

Deliverable D2.1

SUBMERSE Technical Architecture Report

Contractual Date:	28-02-2024
Actual Date:	10-04-2024
Grant Agreement No.:	101095055
Work Package:	WP2
Task Item:	Task 1
Nature of Deliverable:	R (Report),
Dissemination Level:	PU (Public)
Lead Partner:	GÉANT Association
Document ID:	SUBMERSE, Fibre Sensing, DAS, SoP, Technical architecture
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Abstract

This document outlines the current technical architecture of the SUBMERSE system. It covers the principles used to develop the architecture, underlying technologies which acquire data from fibre optic cables, the supporting services to store, process and make available the data.

Funded by
the European Union

© European Future Innovation System Centre on behalf of the SUBMERSE project. The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101095055 (SUBMERSE).

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Document Revision History

[This section to be deleted or hidden before publication of deliverable]

Version	Date	Description of change	Person
1	19-03-24	First draft issued	Chris Atherton (GÉANT)
2	21-03-24	Review and comments	Hannah Mihai (DEIC/DTU)
3	22-03-24	Review and comments	Kurosh Bozorgebrahimi (SIKT)
4	23-03-24	Review and comments	Krzysztof Turza (PSNC)
5	26-03-24	Incorporation of proposed changes and edits to text to clarify document.	Chris Atherton (GÉANT)
6	03-04-24	Quality Review	Carmela Asero (EFIS)
7	03-04-24	Approved and submitted	Carmela Asero (EFIS)

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Executive Summary

The SUBMERSE project endeavours to develop a pan-European system for continuous acquisition and dissemination, specifically designed to meet the needs of European research infrastructures. Utilising sensors attached to submarine fibre-optic communication cables, the project harnesses the capabilities of Distributed Acoustic Sensors (DAS), State of Polarisation (SoP), and Polarimeter technologies. This instrumentation will be installed on at least 3 remote cable systems and each of them must allow the accusation of the generated data by multiple devices simultaneously. The data will be generated in Greece, Norway and Portugal.

This document outlines the different aspects and considerations for the SUBMERSE system architecture, which will enable the deployment of instrumentation and support services capable of enabling fibre sensing.

1 Introduction

The SUBMERSE project aims to develop a multinational, multi stakeholder, research instrument, which is capable of generating and sharing data about the earth from existing, in use submarine telecommunications cables. Such an instrument has not been developed before. This poses significant challenges to how such a system could be set up. It is also an opportunity to act as a pathfinder project to develop technologies which could benefit multiple research communities. This document outlines the current design that is being worked towards by the SUBMERSE consortium partners to realise the aims of the project.

The system itself is composed of multiple parts. These include the sensing equipment, the storage and processing facilities, the dissemination facilities, the network which connects all the equipment together, the access control system, and the synchronisation of time and software across each of the sites. This report will detail the existing envisaged setup which can be applied in general for each of the sites for them to work together. A challenge is that each site has its own specific set of issues which must be addressed to achieve deployment of the system. These challenges may allow a particular course of action to be taken in one site but not in another. However, what is detailed in this report is a general architecture and setup, which accounts for most situations and challenges which a site operator will face. The specific challenges that each separate pathfinder site encounters will not be reported on in this document.

The information presented reflects a snapshot of the current design for the technical setup of the sensing equipment. As the project continues, the design will be refined. What is conveyed represents the thinking at the time of publication and is subject to change as the project progresses.

The development of such an earth observing system represents a new area of expertise development for most of the organisations involved in the project. The technical architecture document will cover the guiding principles that each site would need to adhere to, an overview of the core technologies being used in the project, and descriptions about how to make the data available in a synchronised and scalable way to multiple research communities.

2 Design Principles

The design of each national segment of the SUBMERSE project will need to adhere to certain principles. These principles will provide the bounding for the design and help to ensure that best practice is adhered to. There are two main boundaries that the SUBMERSE project data will need to abide by. These are captured in the data management plan [4], and security and ethics risk register [5]. As the project progresses, input from the data management team, the Security and ethics team, and the wider general assembly will shape the principles which are adhered to in the design, and thus impact on the design itself.

2.1 General Principles

For such a distributed, multi-national system to be created there are some guiding principles, which need to be adhered to.

- User led
- Keep things understandable
- Keep things safe
- Don't do harm
- Expose data and functionality only through service interfaces.
- Reliable, scalable, available (as much as possible).

2.2 Security and Ethics

Due to the type of data that can be collected by the national sites, security is one of the key drivers for the constraints of the project. The generalised security principles that are being followed are:

- Instruments should be nationally controlled.
- Access control must be in place between the site equipment and the outside world.
- All components and software must be trusted.
- Only pre-approved people can access the site equipment (Physical or virtual).
- People can't approve themselves access to equipment or raw data.
- Stored or transported data should always be encrypted.
- Unprocessed Raw data cannot be exposed to the public.
- Data should only be kept for as long as is necessary.

2.3 Data Management Plan

The guiding principles of the data management plan are that the data generated needs to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)[6]. However, there are certain policies which are yet to be established which would contribute to defining how to make the data FAIR. As such data must be:

- As open as possible, as closed as necessary.
- Metadata to closed data should still be made openly accessible.
- Data and metadata should be made available in community determined platforms, following community specific standards.
- While security is an important factor, it should not outweigh the research interests.

3 Architecture

3.1 High level Architecture

Figure 3.1: High level architecture of the national configuration of the SUBMERSE instrumentation system

Each national site aims to conform to a standardised architecture. The architecture and data flow follows five stages: acquisition, raw buffer, national buffer, archiving, and wider dissemination to the global research community.

At the acquisition site, data is generated from the instrumentation and is stamped with a time source as close to the point of acquisition as possible. Data considered non-sensitive is converted into an appropriate format, and shared directly with the trusted repository. The remaining raw data, considered classified, is staged locally before being securely downloaded via an encrypted connection by the national secure buffer. To reduce computational overhead, a secure point to point network connection is to be used.

In the 'raw buffer' part of the architecture, conversion of data from binary files to standardised formats takes place if not already in a format capable for dissemination. The standardised data sets are then searched using machine learning algorithms to detect anomalies and artefacts of interest in the signals. These anomalies are currently checked against known signals and if found to conform to the standard signals, then the data is cleared for release to the national buffer.

In the national buffer, data is stored in a standardised format that allows for scientific analysis. The data in this buffer is kept for as long as possible and is accessible by the privileged users from the national repositories. However, as storage space is filled, the oldest datasets would be deleted. The exception to this would be if the privileged scientific user group identifies a set of files which they wish to keep the raw data. In which case, that data would be stored for the length of the project. Currently it is envisioned that data would be stored for a maximum of 3 months in the national buffer, unless identified by the privileged users as significant.

Data in the national buffer is then downloaded to the national repositories for archiving and further dissemination to the wider global research communities, conforming to the FAIR data principles.

This standardised architecture is current at the time of writing. However, the design and data flow may change as the project progresses, to take into account the use of data, the view on security concerns and ethics, and user stipulations change over time.

A key difference of the project, compared with other projects using fibre sensing technologies, is the distributed number of acquisition sites. The SUBMERSE project intends to deploy the standardised architecture in a number of different sites around Europe and Latin America. These sites were chosen due to the submarine telecommunication cables which land in those locations and the involved participants in the SUBMERSE project.

Figure 3.2: Indicative locations of SUBMERSE instrument sites and the types of experiments which could be performed at each site.

As the project continues, depending on funding and availability of equipment, other site locations will be explored. The other site locations will be selected from submarine cables which are under the auspices of existing SUBMERSE project participants.

3.2 Sensitive Data

To deal with the possibility of collecting potentially sensitive data, several procedures are being initiated by each of the national hosts of the acquisition sites. Responding to, mitigating against, and tackling sensitive data is considered at a national level, not at a project level. Dealing with sensitive data nationally is required due to potential national security implications for releasing unprocessed data globally. However, the guidelines for policies and procedures, which all sites use, are defined at the project level. This allows wider project participation into the types of data that is produced by the national instrumentation and ensures that produced data is available for scientific use in a timely fashion.

3.2.1 Security Policies and Procedures

To ensure that the project acts in a responsible manor the following operational policies are in place for each country:

- A national coordinator is defined for each site
- Each national coordinator works with the national government in their respective territory, in the manner they see fit, to ensure that the national government is aware of the activities being performed by the national instrumentation.
- The national coordinator controls the sensitive data in a manner that conforms to the security mitigation requirements as listed in the risk register and by agreements with their respective national government.
- Data is to be staged in a series of buffers, each with varying levels of controlled access.
- The national coordinator controls access to the raw data that is generated by all the equipment in their respective nation.

There are a number of procedures, which the sites have implemented:

- If a national government wishes for data collection to be suspended, the national site coordinator is to be contacted. The instrumentation will then be switched off for an unannounced emergency maintenance period. The period will be determined through a dialogue between the national coordinator and the national government representatives.
- Data which is released in an automated manner must be from low frequencies (≤ 10 Hz). Recordings of frequencies above 10 Hz must be checked before release to the wider project participants.
- Data which is checked by the national coordinator's team should compare vessel signals with open data sources such as the Ship Automatic Identification System (AIS), to determine if a vessel is operating in the area. If a vessel is not listed, then the data is to not be released until the national government representative gives their approval.

The procedures may change as the project evolves and we create greater operational capabilities.

3.2.2 Frequency Ranges

From discussions with the national site operators, we are conscious that frequency ranges above 10 Hz can contain information which is sensitive. However, data produced at frequencies below 10 Hz and where precise geo-location is not possible are considered safe for release. There are still some frequency ranges below 10Hz which can contain some limited sensitive data. However, obfuscating the precise location and delaying the time to release the data reduces the security risk.

In comparison, the US Navy has a well-defined process for the scrubbing of data. This requires research teams to submit data to the US Navy for processing. The Navy then returns the data back to the research groups after a period with sensitive data removed. This system relies upon the US Navy to process the data. This is not a capability or a capacity that is present in most European navies. It would also reduce strategic autonomy on

European countries if the project was to rely upon the US Navy to provide the data scrubbing. Therefore, the national coordinators are to work closely with the national authorities to build this capability and capacity.

4 Time synchronisation

The data collected from the remote instrument site locations during the experiments must have timestamps. The time stamps allow the data to be synchronised, compared, and processed for further analysis. It requires providing precise time signals to these locations. The locations are thousands of kilometres apart, and the synchronisation of each location should be at the level of a single microsecond. This task is not trivial and requires advanced synchronisation methods using GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) systems. Synchronisation systems will operate in different atmospheric conditions in both southern and northern Europe, moreover a holdover of time signals is required during the unavailability of GNSS signals.

4.1 Time synchronisation requirements

Requirements for time signals delivered to remote locations must meet the following objectives:

- Common time scale at all locations,
- Time synchronisation accuracy better than $1\ \mu\text{s}$ (assuming active synchronisation to a reference signal such as GNSS),
- Holdover performance of time server: accuracy not worse than $1.5\ \mu\text{s}$ in case of GNSS signal unavailability for 2 days,
- Increased accuracy of synchronisation of relative time difference between SoP devices installed at both ends of the same fibre optic cable.

In addition, to enhance the quality of time stamping, the following additional/optional requirements have been defined:

- Monitoring of the quality of generated time signals using time and frequency signals transmitted via fibre optic cable from UTC laboratories,
- Enhancement of time server holdover time using fibre optic connection to UTC laboratory,
- Estimation of the relative difference of time stamping of measurements made with different devices (DAS, SoP, other).

4.2 Time Synchronisation Design

In order to guarantee consistent time stamping of measurement data from geographically distant locations, it is necessary to reference the same stable time source. In addition, to ensure that the results obtained from measurements can be referenced to other experiments (conducted outside of the SUBMERSE project), it is essential that the selected time source is reported to the Bureau International des Poids et Mesures (BIPM), a standards body (i.e. it generates its own realisation of UTC time).

The above requirement imposes the use of GNSS satellite techniques (e.g. GPS signals and UTC-USNO time scale) to implement time synchronisation. This solution will also facilitate direct comparison of the results obtained in the SUBMERSE project with results of other projects' experiments (which currently mostly use time synchronisation using GPS). The alternative solution could be, to use a local UTC time realisation at each measurement point using time transfer over fibre optic links. However, the exact differences between each local

realisation of UTC time are known with a delay of about a month (this is limited by the time when BIPM publishes reports).

To increase security, resilience to satellite signal interference, to guarantee a long time of sustaining high quality time signals (holdover), or finally the ability to monitor these signals, it is recommended to use a dedicated hardware device— a Time Server (TS). This server should have at least one receiver of GNSS signals and have synchronisation outputs to other measurement devices located in the instrumentation site. The preferred way to redistribute the signal to the other devices located in the node should be the PTP 1588v2 [7] protocol and the time server device should have dedicated outputs for each synchronised device.

Figure 4.3: Example high level time stamping architecture for time synchronisation to be implemented at each of the instrumentation sites.

The time server should have a suitable low-noise oscillator to guarantee holdover in case of unavailability of the satellite signal or its significant interference. Guaranteeing a holdover on the level of $1.5 \mu\text{s}$ over 2 days is usually possible with a rubidium oscillator.

Holdover longer than 2 days on the level of $1.5 \mu\text{s}$ or better is possible using synchronisation of the internal clock frequency to a signal provided by a dedicated fibre-optic system from a specialized time laboratory (e.g., UTC laboratory). The 10 MHz signal can be sent from the nearest UTC laboratory (or other laboratory with properly maintained caesium clocks or hydrogen masers) to the time server using fibre-optic time distribution systems such as White Rabbit [8][9]. The fibre-optic connection is not mandatory (especially if the time server is equipped with a good rubidium oscillator) however, it can be very useful in locations where weather conditions may disrupt GNSS signal reception for several days. In this case, such a fibre-optic connection will be used to correct the frequency of the internal clock, not to synchronise the time scale. Therefore, it is not necessary to absolutely

calibrate the fibre-optic system (that is, to accurately determine the signal delay at the system output relative to the reference signal).

Moreover, a fibre-optic connection to a specialised time laboratory will make possible to monitor the quality and correctness of the signals generated by the time server. This will make it possible to detect abnormalities and improper operation of this server. It will allow to detect irregularities and improper operation of the time server.

The connection providing time synchronisation between the time server and individual measuring devices can be made in various standards (typically, time servers have a whole range of synchronisation outputs). However, for ease of management and maintenance, it is recommended to use only one time synchronisation protocol in the whole system – PTP 1588v2. This protocol provides sufficient synchronisation precision (at a level no worse than the previously assumed 1 μ s, and it is supported by a wide range of devices and dedicated server adapters. It is recommended that measurement devices must use the PTP protocol for synchronization. It is also recommended to use different channels for time synchronisation and data transmission.

4.3 Synchronisation of measuring devices with increased accuracy at the two ends of the measured optical fibre

Some applications (measurement scenarios, e.g. tsunami monitoring) require increased accuracy of time synchronisation at both ends of the optical fibre. This may be particularly important for measurements using State of Polarisation (SoP). Here it should be noted that it is not necessary to determine very precisely the time of occurrence of an event, but only the relative delay of its detection at both ends of the optical fibre. In this case, it is not necessary to install very accurate (and therefore expensive) time servers with GNSS receivers at both ends of the fibre optic cable, but only to build a fibre optic time synchronisation system between two measuring devices (e.g. SoP) located at both ends of the fibre optic cable. For this purpose, the PTP protocol supplemented with clock synchronisation, SyncE, [10] can be used. If more accurate synchronisation is required, the White Rabbit or ELSTAB [11] system would be preferable. It should be noted that the source signal for the optical fibre system should be the one generated by the time server located at one end of the fibre.

4.4 Estimating the relative difference time stamping of measurements by different devices

This section will be developed when the first measurement data become available. At that time, the possibility of improving the relative calibration of time (between devices) based on periodic analysis of data and characteristic (the same) events recorded by different measuring devices will be evaluated.

4.5 Time stamping conclusions

A dedicated time server for time synchronisation will guarantee a better resistance to unavailability of external synchronisation signals. Unavailability of time signals can be caused both from failures and interference of the received time signal. It is not possible to guarantee a long holdover and high resistance to attacks and interference (jamming, spoofing) with simple GPS or Galileo signal receivers. Therefore, alternative, complementary time synchronisation via fibre-optic time distribution systems such as White Rabbit should also be explored.

In order to allow the reception of time synchronisation, sensing instruments such as DAS and SoP devices should be equipped with network cards with a dedicated port for PTP 1588v2 synchronisation.

5 Data Acquisition

There exist many ways of sensing disturbances on a fibre optic cable. In the SUBMERSE project we are focusing on Distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) and state of polarisation (SoP). The table of the sensing capabilities below describes the types of sensing techniques, their limitations, and considerations for their deployment.

	Parameter sensed	Maximum Recording distance	Constraints	Cable Requirements	Injected power (dBm)	Data produced per day
DAS (C Band)	Rayleigh backscatter	80-170KM	Can't pass first repeater	Dark fibre	0 to 14 dBm	~7 TB
DAS (L Band)	Rayleigh backscatter	80-170KM	Can't pass first repeater	Accessible L band	0 to 14 dBm	~7 TB
Transponder SoP	Stokes variables	Cable length	Low frequency resolution	DWDM system	0 dBm	3 GB
Polarimeter SoP	Stokes variables	Unknown	Low frequency resolution	DWDM channels	0 dBm	6-250 GB

Table 5.1: Table describing the different sensing techniques being explored in the SUBMERSE project.

Although DAS and SoP are the two focus areas for sensing, within each technology area further considerations must be borne in mind when deploying the instrumentation. The following sections describe those considerations.

5.1 DAS

Distributed acoustic sensing utilises techniques where a laser source is injected into a fibre optic cable and the returned reflections are then interrogated and recorded. The technique makes use of different scattering effects found in electromagnetic spectral physics, where reflections occur each time a light-source hits a medium which contains particles that are smaller than the wavelength of the laser source. There are currently two commonly used scattering effects which are used to detect changes in cables, called Raman [12] and Rayleigh [13] scattering. Raman scattering is in-elastic, which means that the wavelength and the direction of the reflected light changes. Rayleigh scattering is elastic, meaning that only the direction or incidence of the light source changes (not the wavelength).

During the SUBMERSE project, only Rayleigh backscattering techniques are being explored.

Figure 5.4: Principle showing how distributed acoustic sensing works in a fibre optic cable.

By monitoring Rayleigh scattering over time, the changes to the fibre cable as a result of stretch and strain, pressure, and temperature, can be observed. As the detections occur each time a reflection occurs, each reflection point then in effect becomes a sensing point. This means that along the length of a fibre, many (sometimes hundreds of) points can be monitored at varying distances.

As the detection requires a laser signal to be injected into the cable from one side, there is no requirement for an end-to-end connection or session to be established across the full length of the cable for the technology to be used. This means that even if a fibre cable breaks, detections up to and including the point of the break can be detected. However, it should be noted that the sensing capabilities of these techniques reduce the further away from the source of the coherent optical signal. For example, currently the maximum distance for detection for DAS is around 200 km or until the first repeater unit of a submarine telecoms cable. The reason for stopping at the first repeater is due to built-in filters which prevent Rayleigh and Raman backscattering. Newer cable designs may allow for signals to be transported over or around the filters. These are not common and as of writing, there are no known instances of this type of configuration, except through the use of fibre-Bragg gratings [14] which are specially built into submarine repeater units for dedicated maintenance monitoring.

Distributed Acoustic Sensors (DAS) utilise the Rayleigh backscattering technique to detect changes in strain along a fibre optic cable. These strain changes are typically induced by pressure changes in the medium around the cable. In water or air, pressure changes can be caused by sound waves. On Dense Wavelength Division Multiplexing (DWDM) [15] submarine cable systems, Distributed Acoustic Sensors (DAS) can typically be used up until the first repeater unit, or maximum 200 km from the interrogator, to detect pressure changes, temperature changes, and breakages which affect the submarine cable the interrogator is connected to.

There are many ways to deploy a DAS unit on a DWDM system. When combining the DAS with SoP Polarimeters, care must be taken to ensure that the sensing frequencies don't overlap with the other technologies. Given the injected power of the DAS, there is a risk that something could go wrong, and the injected DAS signal could

damage a DWDM system. However, more recently developed DWDM systems have specialised filters built in to prevent harmful signals from damaging the equipment.

To ensure that care is taken not to disrupt telecommunications signals, the DAS signal is to be injected into the L-Band of the optical spectrum on the receiving end of the optical line system. Modern DWDM telecommunications technologies inject communication signals into the 'C' band. For submarine cables, the repeater units also filter out frequencies outside of the 'C' band, unless they have a specialist repeater design which allows these bands to bypass the repeater.

In the case of the SUBMERSE project there is only one cable which we have access to which is repeated: EllaLink [16]. A repeated cable has built in amplifiers to project a laser signal over long distances. The EllaLink cable does not have specially designed repeater units to allow signals outside of the C-Band to pass through them. Therefore, the cable is unable to pass DAS signals past the first repeater unit. All other telecommunications cables that are in use within the project are un-repeated.

Band name	Description	Wavelength range
C-band	conventional ("erbium window")	1530–1565 nm
L-band	long wavelengths	1565–1625 nm

Table 5.2: Overview of C and L band frequency wavelength ranges in optical fibres.

The below diagram describes how a DAS unit is to be deployed on a live telecoms system. The C/L filter should be installed on the receiving fibre of a fibre pair. This allows the DAS L-Band signal to be injected into the fibre without it interfering with the transmissions which occur in the C-Band on the transmit and receive fibres. By deploying the DAS in this way, there is less chance of interfering with data transmissions or with damaging the transmitting DWDM equipment.

Figure 5.5: High-level architecture of a DAS interrogator installed in a coexisting fashion with DWDM equipment.

Injecting the DAS signal into a live telecoms system can pose challenges, especially for the transmission equipment. Due to the filtering, which takes place in the DWDM equipment and the injected DAS signal strength, it is not possible to pass a DAS signal through a DWDM system. However, through field deployments we have shown that it is possible to inject a DAS signal onto a fibre optic pair which is used for optical telecommunications and for the DAS signal to coexist with the DWDM optical signals. This separation of signals between the C and L band means that valuable C band signals can still be utilised for communication. Therefore, reducing the overall cost of the system.

5.1.1 DAS Data Generation

According to scientific literature [2], data rates for DAS may be calculated as:

$$r = \alpha f L / \delta x$$

Where α is the size of one sample on one channel (assumed to be 4 bytes), f is the sampling frequency, L is the total fibre length, and δx is the spatial sampling interval (channel spacing).

To store raw data over a period of 60 days generated from a single DAS device, with a max temporal sampling dependent on a short cable length, the following data rates are estimated to be produced:

- for spatial sampling 2m ~540 TB;
- for spatial sampling 4m ~264 TB;
- for spatial sampling 10m ~104 TB;

The DAS data is produced in a tabular format, and the size of the files can vary depending on the length of cable, the sampling rate, and the sampling interval. The file formats we are focusing on in the SUBMERSE project is HDF5 [19], due to this being a recognised standard in the academic groups we are working with in the project.

The higher sampling frequencies lend themselves more to marine biology use cases. Whereas seismology or oceanography use cases have less requirements for higher frequency sampling. At least, as it is currently understood. Due to this uncertainty, it is not possible to accurately fix the contestants for the sampling. This will be explored further, during the course of the project.

5.2 SoP

The State of Polarization (SoP), in our case in a distributed sensing medium, refers to the orientation and phase of the light (signal) as it travels through the centre of the optical fibre. The term polarised refers to photon (electromagnetic wave) vectors that are oriented in a particular direction. In an ideal world where the core of the optical fibre would be fully cylindrical, the polarised light at the input would be oriented the same way at the output. However, due to the integral properties of the fibre, like birefringence, or external factors like stress, bending, temperature changes, and mechanical or acoustic perturbation, the polarisation changes with distance. The term State of Polarisation (SoP) refers to the vectors, their orientation (in degrees) and phase shift as the light propagates through the fibre. The polarisation has several modes – The best known is linear (vertical/horizontal), circular or elliptical. The light could also be un-polarised, meaning it contains all (mixture) light polarisation types.

Figure 5.6: Depiction of polarised and unpolarised light.

It is worth noticing that birefringence is the key property of “imperfectly” optical fibres, causing the centre of the optical fibre to have a different “refractive index” for different polarisation states and causing light to split into two mutually orthogonal polarisation planes, each travelling at a different speed.

For a graphical representation, the so-called “Poincaré Sphere” is used to illustrate the different kinds and types of light polarisations or their vectors. It shows all possible states as points on a sphere, where the poles represent circular polarisations, the equator represents linear polarisations, and other points represent elliptical polarisations. It maps the light polarisation states using azimuthal and ellipticity angles, similar to the latitude and longitude system on Earth.

Figure 5.7: Example of a Poincaré sphere which can illustrate the different kinds and type of light polarisation [17].

5.2.1 Polarimeter

To be able to detect the SoP and the light scattering caused by the Faraday Effect [18] on the propagating light a dedicated device based on discrete components has been developed. In our use case, distributed submarine sensing infrastructure, we need to distinguish between slow and fast light polarisation rotations and thus provide the ability to detect transitions with extreme sensitivity. Traditional and commercially available solutions, usually integrated into the optical (DWDM) transmission systems as a part of the modulation scheme using polarisation state as on the degree of freedom, are not sufficient. They are mostly based on Digital Signal Processors (DSP), which are fast, but the bottleneck is in the communication interface with insufficient rate limits. Commercially available optical polarimeters are far better, but their typical limitation is the measurement speed with a combination of memory for acquisition samples. The sampling rate of professional polarimeters reaches tens of mega-samples per second, but they are capable of storing up to 1 second of signal in internal memory. For longer-lasting measurements, the samples are averaged over a defined time interval. And the real acquisition throughput is much lower. The logarithmic polarimeters, integrated into the SUBMERSE PolBoxes were designed to overcome this bottleneck using a sampling frequency of 20 kHz due to the expected changes in SoP having frequency footprints up to 10 kHz (a reasonable maximum for mechanical vibration with regard to high water pressure conditions). Its main advantage over the competitors is the ability to capture and pass acquired data at full sampling frequency to the computer for on-the-fly processing.

Figure 5.8: Picture of a SUBMERSE PolBox.

5.2.2 Transponder/PolBox data

The SoP data acquisition through PolBoxes is represented by a total of 3 (Stokes) vectors (columns) where (1-3) being the detection vectors. The first column represents the relative signal power proportionally separated from the signal from which the SoP information is read zero being the reference vector and is formed by averaging the product of the previous vectors. The data is stored at a sampling rate of 20 kHz, i.e. 20 000 records per second, and in HDF5 format [19]. Data storage has two modes: local (delayed) storage and streaming. The local variant stores the SoP data on a PolBox-embedded SSD for one hour. The data is then compressed and sent as gZIP over a secure connection (VPN) to a predefined national storage location in each country that the PolBox is deployed. The second mode is streaming, sending "live" (uncompressed) data to a predefined storage location over the same secure link. The sample screenshot of the SoP HDF5 data can be found below.

	0	1	2	3
0	0.008250126	0.6694477	0.97332734	0.8593881
1	0.008312627	0.6693227	0.9731398	0.8587631
2	0.008312627	0.6692602	0.97301483	0.8585131
3	0.008312627	0.6692602	0.97307736	0.8590131
4	0.008375128	0.6697602	0.97395235	0.8595131
5	0.008250126	0.6694477	0.97213984	0.8583881
6	0.008375128	0.66963524	0.9737024	0.8588256
7	0.008437629	0.6698852	0.9742024	0.8590756
8	0.008437629	0.66919774	0.97351485	0.8585756
9	0.00850013	0.66951025	0.97413987	0.8583881
10	0.008312627	0.6692602	0.9738899	0.85913813
11	0.008375128	0.6684477	0.97376484	0.85913813
12	0.008375128	0.6680727	0.97376484	0.8589506
13	0.008437629	0.6685727	0.97295237	0.8582006
14	0.008312627	0.6683852	0.9744524	0.8595756
15	0.008312627	0.6683227	0.97395235	0.8596381
16	0.008437629	0.6692602	0.9768274	0.86120063
17	0.008250126	0.6683227	0.97451484	0.8600131
18	0.008437629	0.6689477	0.97395235	0.8590131
19	0.008375128	0.6688227	0.9749524	0.8597006
20	0.008187625	0.6675727	0.97376484	0.8592006

Figure 5.9: Example of the contents of a Polbox HDF5 file.

A single SoP device is capable of generating 6 to 250 GB of compressed data per day, so for a single SoP device, storing raw data for 60 days requires ~360 GB to 15 TB.

For data coming from SoP-OTDR devices, the data volume increases proportionally to the number of repeaters. As an example, for the cable from Sines (Portugal) to Fortaleza (Brazil) ~5690 Km with 80 repeaters 29 TB of storage is required.

6 Data Storage

The SUBMERSE project does not rely on a centralised, European scale, data storage service. Due to the national sensitivities of the data that are generated, a distributed and federated approach to data storage is required. This means that each country would set up its data storage in the most practical way possible given the available resources and technologies available. It is also not possible to impose a strict set of specifications on the national configurations without substantial investment. This causes challenges for the project, as there is currently no uniform means for storing data across all sites. However, the approach taken by the project is to remain agnostic to the underlying storage infrastructure. We rely on software abstraction to provide access to the scientific users of the data generated by the project instrumentation.

Data sizes that are being generated vary depending on the instrumentation used. We therefore require easily expandable data storage at each stage.

We are also not able to afford to store all data that is generated. Therefore, we must discard some data that is not of interest at the moment. Considering the environmental impact of the energy consumption of big data centres, this is also beneficial.

There are four stages of storage for the data generated by the project instrumentation: Initial acquisition, raw buffer, open buffer and archiving.

Figure 6.10 Data storage stock and flow model describing the dependencies and influences of the data generation and storage aspects of the SUBMERSE system.

The model is composed of three data generating sources: R1 (Polarimeter SoP), R2 (transponder SoP), and R3 (DAS). These data generating sources are limited by the carrying capacity of their internal hard drive-sizes. It is assumed that the throughput of each device will not be constrained and instead be delivered straight away, unless there is limited disk space (carrying capacity) on the ‘raw buffer’, R4. The ‘raw buffer’ is a stock of data and represents the secure storage area in the SUBMERSE architecture. Within the buffer, data will be checked for security risks and cleared for further release to SUBMERSE partners. The amount of data on the ‘raw buffer’ is determined by the difference between the inflow and outflow of the stock. The inflow being the amount of data from the data sources. The outflow, named ‘Raw buffer outflow rate’ is determined by the time it takes for data to be released and the proportion or percentage of data released.

It should also be noted that we intend to keep some data for training machine learning algorithms. It is envisaged that machine learning will be able to help pipeline development to speed up processing of security data. The disk space has therefore been accounted for in the stock ‘training data’, which is limited in size by the respectively assigned disk space capacity, R5. For the purposes of demonstration this was set to 14 TB, to represent 2 days of data.

Returning back to the main pipeline, after the 'Raw buffer outflow rate', the 'Open data' stock represents the open data buffer that is made available to SUBMERSE participants. The choice of the project is to delete the data after a period of time, due to available funding. The amount of storage required is determined by the delay of the inflow of data into the stock, against the delay in deletion and the proportion of deleted data ('deletion constant') that makes it to the open buffer.

Combining the three stocks of 'raw buffer', 'open data', and 'training data' gives us the total data required by the national coordinator (R6).

If no data was deleted, it is estimated that 1 PB of total data storage resources will be consumed after ~200 days of operation, assuming 7.08 TB of data is produced per day.

However, assuming that 90% data throughput from the raw buffer to the open buffer is achieved after 30 days, and that all data is deleted from the open buffer after 100 days, it is estimated that a total disk space of 660 TB will be required by the national coordinator. A third scenario is presented assuming that 90% data throughput from the raw buffer to the open buffer is achieved after 1 day, and that all data is deleted from the open buffer also after 100 days.

Figure 6.11: Graph A showing disk space usage on 'raw' buffer. Graph B showing disk space usage on the 'open' buffer.

Figure 12: Graph showing combined total disk space used for 3 scenarios.

Further work needs to be invested into understanding the disk space requirements based on the release of data from the raw buffer to the open buffer. We need, however, data to be generated more consistently in order to validate the model. As can be modelled, if the rate of data release can be increased from the raw buffer to the open buffer, then the overall disk space requirements for the project will be lower and researchers can get access to the data they need more quickly. It would also be possible to leverage expandable cloud storage resources, so as to scale storage as demand requires. Project investment in storage resources can then instead be utilised for long-term storage of scientifically valuable data, represented in the ‘training data’ stock in the model.

6.1 Initial acquisition storage

At the time data is generated, there must be sufficient storage in each of the data generating units to store at least 10 days’ worth of data. 10 days is chosen to account for mean time to repair connectivity to a site. The architecture is such that the data is streamed from the units to the raw buffer. On site storage would need to be sized to allow for around 100 TB. This would include the 10 days’ worth of storage plus an additional buffer to allow for errors in calculation. It is advised that the DAS and polarimeter units that are deployed at the instrument site have internal storage. This reduces the reliance on more servers being deployed at the acquisition site.

6.2 Raw buffer

The ‘Raw buffer’ is required to be located in the nation where the data is produced but not necessarily at the instrument site. This is because instrument sites typically are in small buildings and don’t have the facilities or

space to support additional equipment required for storage and processing. There are also data security and digital sovereignty issues which require the data to be initially located in the country of origin. To allow for scaling there is also the possibility that instruments can be moved to other cables or more instruments deployed in-country. This means that the data can be stored at a cloud-based facility within the territory, where scaling is easier. The 'raw buffer' is considered a secure location and so access to this facility should be restricted. The data produced should then be security checked by the designated group who work in conjunction with the national agency who the national coordinator is working with. Once the data has been cleared or scrubbed, it is then released to the 'open data' buffer.

6.3 Open Buffer

The open buffer should be located in the same country/territory as the raw buffer. The size of the open buffer is to be determined by the national coordinator, in consultation with the user groups. The model above can be used to help determine the size of the open buffer. It is estimated that the size of the Open data buffer does not need to be larger than 120 TB if the data on there is deleted after 100 days. Of course, if the delay is extended or not all data is deleted, then more storage would be required.

6.4 Underlying storage technology

The type of underlying storage architecture used in the raw or open buffers could be file-, block- or object storage; the project is agnostic to the underlying hardware infrastructure in this case. However, whichever hardware or cloud data storage approach is used, it must be possible for the storage system to share data with multiple users via remote interfaces with external storages. That could be with an API or with pre-established remote access enabled through AAI. In which case, the storage system would need to support SAML or OIDC/OAuth 2.0 [20].

6.5 Archives

As elaborated upon in the data management plan, the project wishes to not create a parallel infrastructure compared to the existing infrastructures that already support the different scientific communities, we are approaching or collaborating with. Therefore, long-term data storage and archiving will be handled by the user communities in the project. From an architectural perspective, the underlying technology of the user communities' archives is beyond the scope of the technical architecture work package. However, it should be noted that the SUBMERSE instrumentation could generate up to 7.8 TB of data per day.

Not all of this data will likely be useful for each of the communities, therefore it is recommended that most of the data is discarded. There are various approaches for how this can be done, such as data decimation or down sampling, reduction of measurement points, or only saving snapshots of scientifically relevant instances.

It is difficult to determine which is the best approach. Currently communities would prefer to not delete any data, due to the potential for containing scientifically relevant information. Further investigations will be made as the project continues to explore which of the approaches outlined. For the moment, all data will be saved.

7 Data processing

The SUBMERSE project endeavours to develop a pan-European system for continuous acquisition and dissemination, specifically designed to meet the needs of European research infrastructures. Utilising sensors attached to submarine fibre-optic communication cables, the project harnesses the capabilities of Distributed Acoustic Sensors (DAS), State of Polarisation (SoP), and Polarimeter technologies. This instrumentation will be installed on at least 3 remote cable systems and each of them must allow the accusation of the generated data by multiple devices simultaneously.

The raw measurements generated by sensors must be pre-processed before they are stored in the archive. Data originating from various device types necessitates meticulous formatting and standardisation to ensure uniformity in storage format. Additionally, a critical aspect of the data processing pipeline involves thorough cleaning procedures to pre-emptively mitigate the risk of inadvertently releasing sensitive measurements, particularly from applications with military implications. A key focus lies in the analysis phase, where the data undergoes scrutiny to identify occurrences of predefined vulnerable events — those instances that must not be disclosed to the public. Upon detection of such events, a rigorous scrubbing process is promptly executed to eliminate any traces of sensitive information. The cleaned data is stored in a central repository in the data centre. In addition, raw, unprocessed data from the past few months is stored in a buffer. This data can be used to train algorithms to classify and scrub data.

The pre-processing of raw data has the following objectives:

- Standardise the format of data and its metadata from different types of devices.
- Propose and develop a proof of concept for data filtering algorithms.
- Analyse data to detect anomalies to help define new samples of sensitive measurements.
- Detection and hiding of predefined measurement patterns.

7.1 Data Pre-Processing System Design

The architecture of the pre-processing system focuses on the preliminary analysis of data and its delivery to the repository.

Data from different types of devices differ mainly in volume and interpretation. SoP provides measurements averaged over the entire cable, while DAS collects measurements from multiple locations on the fibre simultaneously. DAS has by far the higher rate of data generation when compared to SoP. In order to understand what is contained in the data it first needs to be processed. This means the system architecture will be mainly impacted by the size of the DAS data processing requirements.

The system architecture comprises two key elements: sensor devices situated in proximity to the fibre-optic cable and a centralised data centre, which also serves as a data buffer. Initial computations for small data sets can be conducted locally on servers embedded within the devices responsible for data generation. However, when dealing with potentially vast volumes of data from a single Distributed Acoustic Sensors (DAS) device, the computational demands surpass the capacity of the local server. Consequently, it is necessary not to process raw data locally; instead, the data should be transmitted directly to a central data centre, to the scrubbing servers for pre-processing and cleansing. Subsequently, the refined data is forwarded to the archival system. This approach alleviates the hardware constraints on the local server. By relying on data centres, substantial computing power can be leveraged, in comparison. If required, the option to effortlessly augment processing

and storage resources allows the resource usage to scale up or down as required. This will enable the use of more advanced artificial intelligence techniques for data processing. Thus, it is recommended to process raw data in a data centre where the infrastructure allows for easy scaling of allocated resources for scrubbing servers in the form of virtual machines or docker containerisation, such as VMware or Kubernetes.

Figure 7.13: General data processing architecture with SoP and DAS.

To ensure optimal data transfer from a single DAS unit, a direct and dedicated connection between the unit and the data centre of at least 1 Gbps is required. A 10 Gbps link is preferred. Such a link will ensure low latency in data transfer. The latency resulting from data transmission will be negligibly small compared to the latency resulting from data generation and processing. It is preferred to encrypt the connection between the router at the cable landing station to the data centre via a L2 VPN. This would allow encryption of the raw data transmitted from the local server to the data centre without impacting on computational performance of the cable landing station local server.

7.2 Scrubbing Data

Data scrubbing is aimed at identifying and filtering out data that may contain potentially sensitive measurements. This involves the exclusion of measurements from specific areas of the cable or the entire files if they exhibit detected signatures. The detection process can be set up in the form of predefined frequency ranges that indicate a given type of signal. More complex will be the use of artificial intelligence algorithms that classify data as sensitive or non-sensitive. Data processing takes place in two locations: on a server located close to the sensor and on scrubbing servers in the data centre.

The local server processes the raw data produced directly by the DAS and Polarimeter devices. To obtain the highest accuracy in time-stamping measurements, it is preferable to directly time-tag the data at the sensor. In cases where this is not feasible, the time stamping process is carried out on the local server, or as a last resort at the data centre. Time stamping is the first operation on data to obtain the closest possible accuracy of the time interval in which the data was collected. Data cleaning on the local servers should be very simple and fast due to the low computing power of this machine. Therefore, data cleaning here should be limited to a set of simple filter rules such as filtering selected areas of the cable in the case of DAS, or certain time intervals. Data

that has been filtered in this way will not be further passed or stored in the cable landing station data buffer. The remaining data can be transmitted via a secure connection to the data centre for further processing.

Figure 7.14: Data processing scheme on a local server.

Data transmitted to the data centre can be decrypted (if encrypted via Layer 3 transmission) and saved in the ‘raw’ buffer storage. This data is considered classified at this point. The actual data scrubbing then takes place. Data coming from the DAS, due to its volume, will require a cascade of data classification algorithms to quickly identify data that does not contain sensitive measurements. Only data that potentially contains sensitive information will be processed by all algorithms. For example, if the data contains only noise that occurs if nothing was happening in the area around the fibre, then there is no need to use advanced deep learning techniques to process this data and only statistical analysis in the time and frequency domain will be sufficient. Due to the high correlation between successive measurement points in the cable, it is not necessary to classify each channel. Therefore, only a subset of channels distant from each other by a certain amount will be processed. It is possible to classify all channels, however, this will significantly increase the requirements for computing power and may increase the delay resulting from scrubbing data.

Figure 7.15: Data processing scheme on scrubbing server in a data centre.

7.3 Format of Output data

The incoming data from the DAS facilities is in HDF5 format, which allows both measurements and their metadata to be stored in a single file. All data types will be converted to this format and stored in the buffer. It is possible to save data in another format, however, this will require an increase in computing resources.

7.4 Processing Latency

By default, DAS files contain data in the range of 10 seconds. These files can be processed independently or in groups of several. We can detect events that fall entirely within the processed time interval. This means that processing several files at the same time will enable the detection of longer events. However, processing several files concurrently introduces greater delays and requires more computing resources.

In the case of simple raw data processing involving only frequency filtering for each 10 s-file independently with maximum temporal sampling for instance 1 kHz with 100 km fibre length and spatial sampling 4 m, the delay resulting from processing will be >1 min.

For more advanced pattern-detection-algorithms, latency may increase, and computational resource requirements will increase

8 Data Dissemination and AAI

To meet the ambitions of the project data accessibility, authentication and authorization infrastructure, and monitoring is required for the dissemination of the generated data to the research infrastructures. A persistent identifier (PID) service to manage the persistence and provenance of the data is also required to ensure FAIR use of the data produced. Below we describe the architecture of the areas outlined.

8.1 PID Service Support

The data that will be produced by each site is expected to be in the order of 7 TB per day and they will need to be stored for the foreseeable future according to the FAIR principles. To this end, SUBMERSE chose to PIDs to ensure that data are findable for the foreseeable future. The granularity of PID assignment will be defined according to the Data Management Plan and the requirements of WP3.

8.1.1 Description of Persistent Identifiers (PID) architecture

A PID is a unique identifier (label) assigned to a resource, digital object or entity, designed to facilitate long-term referencing and accessibility. Unlike regular identifiers, which may change or become obsolete, PIDs are intended to provide long-term stability and reliability for referencing and accessing digital resources. PIDs are commonly used in scholarly communication, research data management, digital archives, and other domains, where reliable identification and linking of digital objects are essential. The primary characteristics of PID include uniqueness, persistence, resolvability (the ability to be resolved to a location or metadata), and interoperability (compatibility across different systems and platforms). Overall, PIDs play a critical role in enhancing the discoverability, accessibility, and long-term preservation of digital information in various domains. PIDs are crucial components of the digital information ecosystem, providing a means to uniquely identify and reference digital objects such as publications, datasets, software, and other research outputs.

The PID structure consists of two parts separated by a forward slash (/): the prefix and the postfix. The prefix is a single number assigned to a particular institution or individual, serving as a namespace identifier. Multiple postfixes, each represented by a unique alphanumeric string of characters, may be associated with a single prefix. Together, the prefix and postfix uniquely identify the data and its location via URL. This system ensures that the data can be reliably referenced and accessed over time, even if its location or metadata changes. **SUBMERSE will use its own Prefix. Further work is required to determine if we are to setup our own handle server or use an existing one, as well as to decide if we are to use Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs). Such work will be elaborated upon in the remaining time of the project.**

8.1.2 Managing Persistent Identifiers

Managing PIDs involves several key tasks and considerations to ensure their effective use and long-term sustainability. Assigning unique PIDs to digital objects is the first step in managing persistent identifiers. This process involves registering the PID and associating it with the correct metadata describing the identified resource. Managing metadata associated with PIDs is essential for enhancing the discoverability, accessibility, and usability of digital objects. This includes creating and maintaining descriptive metadata describing the identified resources, updating metadata as needed to reflect changes or updates to the resources, and ensuring metadata quality and consistency across the PID ecosystem.

Managing the lifecycle of persistent identifiers based on the Data Management Plan involves also updating or deactivating identifiers as needed and ensuring compliance with relevant policies and standards. Considerations include implementing policies for identifier versioning, archival preservation, and retirement. This includes data in various states of movement and storage like *dataflow*, *buffer storage*, *storage and repository data*.

8.1.3 Managing a PID

Managing a PID consists of minting, resolving and updating the persistent identifiers. With regards minting, this registration process involves, as already mentioned, providing metadata about the identified resource, such as title, creation date, access rights and more, to facilitate discovery and retrieval by users and systems. GRNET PID Service provides a, for us, suitable HTTP API to mint PIDs.

To resolve the PID, the ePIC resolution mechanism [21] allows users and systems to resolve PIDs to the associated resource or metadata. Actionable PIDs are also supported so as to facilitate access to the identified resources. Again, the GRNET Service provides a HTTP API to resolve and update the PID either directly to the metadata page, or the resource. The GRNET service also allows part of a PID to be updated, allowing greater flexibility and scalability in deployment.

8.1.4 Reverse lookup mechanism

A reverse lookup mechanism will be enabled. This mechanism helps prevent the unintentional duplication of identifiers. Users can verify whether a URL has already been assigned a PID before requesting a new one. This helps avoid duplication of URLs, and addresses several challenges associated with relying solely on URLs for referencing and accessing digital resources, reducing the risk of conflicting or redundant identifiers. The reverse lookup mechanism helps prevent the unintentional duplication of identifiers.

8.1.5 PID Tombstone

When data referenced in a PID is no longer available, a tombstone page can be created. A PID tombstone refers to a placeholder or marker that remains in place after a PID has been deactivated. It serves as a traceable record of the deleted data and records the previously assigned identifier and typically includes information about the deletion, such as the reason for deletion, date of deletion, and any alternative identifiers or access instructions. This allows users and systems to understand its history and providing context for any references that may have relied on the deleted PID. PID tombstones play a crucial role in preserving the integrity of the digital ecosystem by preserving the metadata and ensuring transparency and accountability in the management of PIDs. Additionally, PID tombstones can facilitate the resolution of broken links by directing users to alternative identifiers or access points, thereby mitigating the impact of data deletions on the discoverability and usability of digital objects.

This action is just an update to the PID metadata.

8.2 Service Monitoring

The current Work Plan of SUBMERSE calls for at least 3 national sites to be deployed (Portugal, Greece and Norway) and according to the architecture described in chapter 3 a number of services will need to be running reliably in order for the workflow to be operational. The Service Monitoring sub-activity is responsible to monitor the reliability and availability and the status of the services of this infrastructure. The proposed solution is based on Argo monitoring [3] and will monitor a wide range of services and provide operational insights for different built-in key performance indicators. A modular, pluggable architecture will be used so that the service can easily support a wide range of integrations as needed. There are several things to consider when monitoring a Service. The more complex a system gets, the harder it gets to monitor. Argo Monitoring follows a plan for solving these kinds of challenges and provides an easy path to gain powerful insights. The Argo Monitoring service starts monitoring the service by checking the liveness/health of the service. The main focus though is to check the availability and reliability of the services as well as groups of services by simulating the actions that the respective user would do interacting with it. For instance, in the case of a file transfer server (FTP), the service tries to transfer, save and delete a file in the server. These tests are performed at regular random intervals (e.g. every hour or every 15 minutes) and their results are recorded to be included in the measuring of the availability and reliability of the service. The service supports different profiles for creating the topology and grouping of services and the algorithm for calculating the availability and reliability of services. The calculations are performed in big data management and processing infrastructures (use of Apache Flink platform) which provide results both in real time and their correction at regular intervals. The service publishes the results of its calculations in real time, thus allowing the creation of a control panel displaying the status of the services (through a special interface that has been created). Such a service provides the possibility of timely notification (alerts via email as well as SMS and slack messages) of administrators in case of a detected error. Argo monitoring provides a modern and comprehensive web user interface in which users can easily view details and results (status results and availability results scores) on items monitored. Users can navigate through the different layers of topology (groups, services, endpoints) and with various levels of granularity (monthly, daily, etc...)

Figure 8.16: Screenshot of the initial deployment of SUBMERSE Monitoring.

The Argo Monitoring service provides a flexible and scalable framework for monitoring status, availability and reliability of a wide range of services provided by infrastructures with medium to high complexity. Argo generates reports using customer defined profiles (e.g. for SLA management, operations, etc.). During the report generation, Argo takes into account custom factors such as the importance of a specific service endpoint and

scheduled or unscheduled downtimes. In order to have a successful deployment of the monitoring for SUBMERSE one needs to do the following

- Define the Topology: One of the main sources of truth used in the Monitoring Service is the topology. It helps to discover and map relationships between services/resources. Via the topology the owner may have in-depth visibility into the infrastructure, by enabling the Monitoring Service to categorise, classify, and finally monitor the services in it. Topology includes all the necessary information about how an infrastructure is structured and organised.
- For each service endpoint define the necessary metrics. A metric is a procedure that checks specific functionality of a given service.
- Create the necessary profiles, a Metric Profile that is used to associate a Service with the corresponding metrics and an Aggregation Profile defines how to aggregate service statuses into higher hierarchical grouping (i.e. a service_group) status results. They are actually used to define logical rules on how to aggregate individual service status computations into groups.
- Create the required reports.: Argo Monitoring Service is checking the services at regular intervals. It actually runs explicit tests (checks) in order to assess the status of the service. The result of the checks decides on the state of the service at a given point in time. Argo Monitoring service using its analytics engine (a big-data friendly platform), analyses the stream of collected Metric Data, and is able to apply calculations on all the levels of the topology. It provides the following types of reports.
 - Status Timeline results: This is a report of the status of the monitored item/group of items, during the monitoring time. Knowing the timeline, provides information about the condition of the monitored item, helps to spot the most problematic metrics and decide about them. It is of major significance especially knowing when the monitored item is in a CRITICAL status, or it is in 'OK' status.
 - Availability/Reliability (A/R) results for the monitored item or a group of monitored items.
 - Flapping Items: Argo Monitoring service analyses the status timelines in different levels, detects the flapping patterns and creates a report with the list of the most problematic monitored items.
 - Performance Monitoring: Beyond providing monitoring of the status and the availability/reliability of services, the Argo Monitoring Service is able to enrich the monitoring experience by providing insights on the performance of the services. Service performance monitoring allows service administrators to be proactive by tracking resource consumption, response times, and other performance metrics as well as predict potential issues so they can resolve problems before they impact end users.

So far, we deployed the SUBMERSE monitoring tenant with only basic metrics (http check) for a few pilot services. As next steps as soon as services become operational the team will work with the Service operators.

8.3 AAI Support

The task will provide coordinated consultancy, support and guidelines on how to control access to data through the eduTEAMS Authentication Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI). The eduTEAMS service enables secure access to resources and services running on different platforms and using different technology stacks. The task will

support the configuration and integration of Service Providers (SPs) from research infrastructures and public institutions which require access to the data such as the Automatic Multicast Tunnel (AMT) Streams and other services that will be developed by WP2 and WP3 for dissemination of data.

Service owners have the option to connect their services to eduTEAMS using either OpenID Connect (OIDC) or SAML2 protocols. Service registration requests need to be submitted through the eduTEAMS service registration form. All registration requests are subject to review by the eduTEAMS Support team. The requester details, including name, email, and identifier, are pre-filled from their eduTEAMS Profile, with additional organisation information required if not already included in the eduTEAMS Profile. Service owners need to supply the legal entity name and website responsible for the service, along with essential service details such as name, description, website URL, and logo URL. Contact information, including email addresses for administrative, security, helpdesk, and technical contacts, must also be provided. Service owners also need to supply the URLs for the service provider policies, including privacy policy, acceptable usage policy/terms of use, and incident response policy, and also indicate compliance with the GÉANT Data Protection Code of Conduct [22], the Sirtfi security framework [23], and the Research and Scholarship entity category [24]. When registering a SAML2 service provider, owners need to specify eduGAIN publication status and provide entity ID or metadata URL, while OIDC registration involves selecting supported OAuth 2.0 grants, specifying the client type (public or confidential), and providing redirect URLs. Upon form submission, owners receive a confirmation page, and applications are subsequently reviewed by the eduTEAMS Support team, with notifications sent via email. The service registration process is further detailed in the eduTEAMS service registration guide.

Following the acceptance of the service registration request, the service owner needs to configure their service based on the chosen protocol, whether OIDC or SAML. The eduTEAMS documentation includes configuration examples for commonly used OIDC and SAML client libraries.

Once the service is configured, user attributes will be accessible in the form of OIDC claims or SAML attributes. These encompass a range of information crucial for user authentication and authorisation:

- Community User Identifier
- Display Name
- Given Name
- Family Name
- Email address
- Affiliation within Home Organization
- Affiliation within eduTEAMS
- Groups
- Assurance
- ORCID
- eduTEAMS Username
- SSH Public Keys

Attributes form the basis of the information which is shared via SAML or OIDC. Claims to the attributes are documented in the 'attributes available to relying parties' page. Attribute claims marked as 'Mandatory' will always be available to the service requesting or claiming the attribute. Attribute claims marked as 'Optional' will be made available under certain circumstances. For example, some attribute claims can be available only if the respective attribute claims are released by the home Identity Provider (IdP) of the user.

8.4 Dissemination System

As this aspect of the system requires data in multiple countries to be made available, it is too early in the project to fully tackle this activity. This work will be elaborated on during the next iteration of the architecture report.

The activity will investigate with work package 3 task 4 the methods to integrate the data produced from the distributed research instruments to the EIDA storage archive [25], with a focus on scalability and real time streaming. To that extent the task will investigate solutions such as Apache Spark [26] and RUCIO [27] to serve as the dissemination system.

9 Conclusion

The SUBMERSE project is a pan-European distributed earth observation instrument. The locations of the data producing instrumentation are in Greece, Portugal, and Norway. The means of producing data relies upon a mixture of technologies, which detect changes to laser signals deployed on submarine fibre optic telecommunications cables. The technologies being investigated are distributed acoustic sensors (DAS) and state of polarisation (SoP). Alongside DAS and SoP, a consistent time source needs to be provided. This could be via satellite navigation systems or a network time protocol. The time source allows the data which is generated to be accurately compared with data produced from other locations. It is also a pre-cursor for allowing finer resolution of SoP sensing.

Once data is produced, it will need to be transported to a processing facility for declassification. It is the opinion of the work package team working on this document that more scalable processing and storage can be found at a centralised national processing facility, rather than performing all processing and storage at the points of acquisition.

Once data is processed to identify and scrub sensitive data it is then to be stored for a limited period of time (as of writing, it is proposed to be 100 days once the data streaming aspect of the system is enabled. Until then, all data is being captured).

During the limited availability period, research groups will have the opportunity to download the data to perform further investigations and derive higher value data sets by further processing of the raw data.

In order to provide access to the data stored in each country, a centralised project AAI service utilising eduTEAMS will be enabled. In addition, a monitoring service will be enabled to ensure the quality of the services.

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Glossary

SUBMERSE	Submarine Cables for Research and Exploration
DAS	Distributed Acoustic Sensor
SoP	State of Polarisation
PID	Persistent Identifier,
NREN	National Research and Education Network
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
AAI	Authentication Authorization Infrastructure
AMT	Automatic Multicast Tunnelling
GÉANT	Pan-European Research and Education Network
SSH	Secure Shell
Sirtfi	Security Incident Response Trust Framework for Federated Identity
IdP	Identity Provider
SP	Service Provider
AIS	Automatic Identification System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
UTC-USNO	United States Naval Observatory time standard
BIPM	Bureau International des Poids et Mesures
TS	Time Server
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
ELSTAB	Electronically Stabilised time and frequency over fibre
Galileo	A European owned and run GNSS.
dBm	Decibels relative to 1 milliwatt
DWDM	Dense Wavelength Division Multiplexing
EllaLink	A company and an optical submarine cable system linking Europe and South America
DSP	Digital Signal Processors
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
OIDC	OpenID Connect
OAuth 2.0	Open Authorization standard
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
HTTP API	Hyper Text Transfer Protocol Application Programming Interface
ePIC	ePIC Persistent Identifier Consortium
Sirtfi	Security Incident Response Trust Framework for Federated Identity
URL	Unique Resource Location
EIDA	European Integrated Data Archive